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Modellierung und Analyse der embryonalen Strukturbildung in Fischmuskeln

(Modelling and Analysis of the Chevron Formation in the Fish Myotome)

Diplomarbeit
zur Erlangung des wissenschaftlichen Grades
Diplom-Physiker

vorgelegt von

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2010

Eingereicht am 25.01.2010

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Kurzdarstellung

Die Körpersegmente von Fischen zeigen eine gezackte Form, die als Chevronform bezeichnet wird. An der schrägen Orientierung von Fischgräten ist sie klar ersichtlich. In der Fachliteratur wurde vorgeschlagen, dass die Chevronform optimal für die wechselseitigen Biegebewegungen von Fischen während des Schwimmens ist. Viel weniger ist über die physikalischen Mechanismen, die der Entwicklung dieser Form während der Embryogenese zugrunde liegen, bekannt.

In dieser Diplomarbeit werden wir die vorgeschlagenen Mechanismen prüfen und befinden sie für ungenügend. Basierend auf unserer Datenanalyse der Segmentformänderungen schlagen wir einen neuartigen Mechanismus vor, um die anfängliche Chevronbildung zu erklären. Ein mathematisches Modell der Wechselwirkungen zwischen sich entwickelnden Muskelfasern und Segmentgrenzen wird aufgestellt und es werden analytische und numerische Lösungen des Modells durchgeführt. Die Modellvorhersagen für die anfängliche Chevronbildung werden durch Vergleich mit den experimentellen Daten bestätigt.

Wir diskutieren mögliche Erweiterungen unseres Modells, um damit Aussagen über spätere Abschnitte der Chevronbildung machen zu können. Desweiteren schlagen wir Experimente zur Bestätigung unserer „Pioniermuskel-Hypothese“ vor und zeigen offene Fragen zur Chevronbildung auf, die in dieser Diplomarbeit nicht behandelt werden konnten.

Abstract

The body segments of fish have a folded shape, called chevron, which is obvious from the oblique orientation of fish bones. The chevron shape has been proposed to be optimal for the alternating body movements during swimming. Much less is known about which physical mechanisms underly the development of this shape during embryogenesis.

In this thesis we will review which mechanisms have been proposed in the literature and show that they are insufficient. Based on our data analysis of segment shape changes, we propose a novel mechanism to explain the beginning chevron development. A mathematical model of the interactions between developing muscle fibers and segment boundaries is derived and solved analytically and numerically. Model predictions are verified for early chevron formation by comparison to experimental data.

We discuss possible extensions of our model to account for additional properties of later stages in chevron formation. Furthermore we propose experiments that could validate our “Muscle Pioneer Hypothesis” and state open questions concerning chevron pattern development that could not be discussed in this thesis.

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1 Introduction

The question for the function of the folded shape, called chevron shape, of the body segments of fish has been a long standing problem [Chevrel, 1913; Greene and Greene, 1913] and is still relevant today [van Leeuwen et al., 2008]. The shape was proposed to be optimal for fish swimming, despite ongoing disputes why it is optimal and how this optimum is achieved [Nursall, 1956; Willemse, 1966]. “Constraints by the physical properties of matter, by functional demands and by phylogenetic limitations...” [Van Leeuwen, 1999] have been considered to explain the chevron pattern. The question for mechanisms that are involved in the emergence of this shape during development from the fertilized egg cell towards the mature fish, and how they constrain the function and shape, was rarely addressed [Raamsdonk et al., 1974a; Turner, 2007]. This thesis aims to fill a bit of this gap in knowledge about fish development.

We begin with a review of the embryonic development of fish using the example of zebrafish in chapter 2. Readers with knowledge about somitogenesis and myogenesis in fish might skip this chapter.

In chapter 3 the literature about the relation of fish segment shape and its function is reviewed. Then the current hypotheses for mechanisms that drive chevron pattern formation in fish will be discussed. It will get clear that they do not suffice as explanation. Furthermore we report developmental processes that influence the correct shaping, by analysing experiments with mutant fish.

Using our experimental data (chapter 4) and current findings in muscle cell differentiation we formulate a new hypothesis for a mechanism to explain chevron formation in chapter 5. We will derive a mathematical model for quantification.

The results of our model and their comparison to experimental data will be presented in the next chapter.

Then follows the discussion of our obtained results in chapter 7. Ideas for extensions of our model for later stages of chevron development will be given. Also, we propose experiments that could validate our hypothesis and state open questions

1 Introduction

concerning chevron pattern development. Alternative modelling approaches will also be discussed.

We finish the thesis with a conclusion of what has been achieved.

2 Biological Background

2.1 Chevron Pattern Development in Fish

In this chapter we review the development of a fish embryo. We will emphasize on the development of the pattern in which the fish's trunk muscles will arrange. This complex shape is referred to as chevron shape [Hoar et al., 1969; Cibois et al., 2010]. In salmon the shape is most prominently seen (Fig. 2.1(a)). In this work we will refer to and also use data of zebrafish (Fig. 2.1(b) and (c)) because it is a commonly used model organism in current scientific research [Sprague et al., 2007].

The word chevron is commonly used to describe a V-shaped pattern [Merriam-Webster, 2010], but also for patterns with multiple folds, e.g. in geology [Bayly, 1974], also for polymers and liquid crystals in material science [Singer, 1993; Read et al., 1999].

In this work we will use the term chevron pattern to describe the shape of the fish's trunk muscles. We will also use the terms V-shape or W-shape if we need to be more specific.

We will need some anatomical terms for proper description of directions within the fish, which are briefly explained in Fig. 2.2.

2.1.1 Early Embryonic Development

The development of the zebrafish starts with the fertilized egg cell (Fig. 2.3(a)). This cell divides until a cell number of about a thousand cells is reached (Fig. 2.3(b)), which then start epiboly, the spreading of the proliferative cells over the yolk cell (Fig. 2.3(c)). During epiboly additional cell rearrangements and movements start. Cells stream towards the dorsal side (Fig. 2.3(d)), converge in the mediolateral direction and thereby lengthen the anteroposterior axis. Ten hours post fertilization (hpf), the tail bud, a distinct swelling at the posterior end of the embryo, appears (Fig.

2 Biological Background

(a) Salmon fillet. Blue line marks chevron pattern.

(b) Zebrafish. Fish spans about 3 cm from left to right. From BBC News [2000]

(c) Transparent zebrafish larva. Chevron visible. Larva spans about 4 mm from left to right. From [van Eeden et al., 1996]

Figure 2.1: Salmon and Zebrafish. Both show chevron structures and have a similar embryonic development [personnel communication with Andy Oates].

Figure 2.2: Anatomical Directions. Anterior is towards the head, posterior is towards the tail. Dorsal is towards the back, ventral is towards the belly. Left and right sides may also be referred to as lateral sides. The central region of left-right axis is called medial. We may also use the term mediolateral axis, meaning an axis from the medial region towards either left or right. From Wikipedia [2010]

2.1 Chevron Pattern Development in Fish

Figure 2.3: Stages in early embryonic zebrafish development. Development times given in hours post fertilization (hpf) are valid for a temperature of 28.5 °C. Panels (a) to (d) are camera lucida sketches. Panel (e) is a brightfield image. Animal pole is to the top. One cannot distinguish dorsal and ventral in figures (a) to (c). In Fig. (d) and (e) the dorsal side, where the back will form, is to the right. Note that the ventral side is thinner because cells stream dorsally. The arrowhead in figure (e) marks the tail bud, the arrow marks the future head. Scale bar 250 μm . From Kimmel et al. [1995]

2.3(e))[Kimmel et al., 1995].

2.1.2 Somitogenesis

Somitogenesis is the segmentation of the vertebrate anteroposterior axis into pairs of similar tissue units called somites [Cooke and Zeeman, 1976; Baker et al., 2008]. The tissue from which the somites are formed is called presomitic mesoderm. In zebrafish there develop about 30 somites [Kimmel et al., 1995]. The first somites appear about 10 hpf, just past the bud stage (Fig. 2.4(a)). Somite formation begins anteriorly and a new one is formed posteriorly every 20-30 minutes (Fig. 2.4(b)). Newly formed somites have an approximate shape of a sphere (Fig. 2.4(c)). In further embryo development somites differentiate into sclerotome, dermatome and myotome [van Eeden et al., 1996]. Among others the sclerotome will develop into bone and cartilage [Kimmel et al., 1995]. The sclerotome differentiates comparatively late and is made up of a minor part of the somitic cells in zebrafish. The dermatome gives rise to a part of the skin [van Eeden et al., 1996]. The major part of the somite will form the myotome [Stickney et al., 2000]. The metameric arrangement of the

2 Biological Background

Figure 2.4: Somitogenesis. Fig. (a) and (b) are camera lucida sketches. Animal pole is to the top, dorsal to the right, scale bar $250 \mu\text{m}$. From 11 hpf to 14 hpf there developed 7 somites corresponding to 2-3 somites every hour. Fig. (c) and (d) are Normarski views, dorsal to the top, anterior to the left, scale bar $50 \mu\text{m}$. From Kimmel et al. [1995].

somites is kept by the myotomes, therefore we call the myotome from somite one: myotome one, and so on [Kimmel et al., 1995].

Throughout this thesis we will use the terms myotome, somite and segment as synonyms.

2.1.3 Myogenesis

As myogenesis we here term the formation of muscle tissue in the somite. In the presomitic mesoderm a class of cells called adaxial cells exists in the medial region (Fig. 2.5). These will travel through the myotome to the lateral region, elongate and form a superficial layer of slow muscle cells [Stickney et al., 2000]. A subclass of these cells, the muscle pioneers, stay adjacent to the medial region. These are the first cells to elongate and to show muscle cell properties [van Eeden et al., 1996]. The bulk of the cells in the myotome will become another type of muscle cell, called fast muscle [Stickney et al., 2000]. The elongation of the fast muscle cells is initiated by the migrating slow muscle cells [Henry and Amacher, 2004].

2.1.4 Chevron Formation

At a temperature of 28.5°C the somites appear as spheres (like the somites in Fig. 2.4(d)) until the 7 somite stage [van Eeden et al., 1996] and until the 12 somite stage at 22°C [Raamsdonk et al., 1974a].

2.1 Chevron Pattern Development in Fish

Figure 2.5: Cross-section through a zebrafish myotome at 24 hpf. On the left side the blue lines show the trajectories of adaxial cells which form the slow muscle fibers. Modified from Stickney et al. [2000].

Then the somites become chevron-shaped [Kimmel et al., 1995; Henry et al., 2005], but the first 3-4 boundaries remain barely chevron shaped [Raamsdonk et al., 1974a; Kimmel et al., 1995]. The apex of the V points anteriorly (Fig. 2.1(c), 2.6(a)). Tail somites (18-35) behave differently as they change shape immediately after somite formation [Raamsdonk et al., 1974a, 1977].

Interestingly muscle pioneer elongation and chevron pattern formation happen simultaneously [Kimmel et al., 1995].

The embryo starts movements in the 16 somite stage [Raamsdonk et al., 1979] and hatches about 3 days post fertilization.

2.1.5 Development after Hatching

The somites stay V-shaped until about 3 weeks after hatching (Fig. 2.6(b)). Then the ventral and dorsal ends of the somite will start to fold in anterior direction, a W-shape starts to emerge [Raamsdonk et al., 1974a]. Another 3 weeks later the somites have the adult W-shape (Fig. 2.6(c)). Opposed to that salmon already show W-shaped somites when they hatch (Fig. 2.7(a)).

The term W-shape does not adequately describe the real shape of a myomere but only what is seen in a lateral section of the fish. The earliest detailed descriptions of fish myotomes were done for the king salmon by Greene and Greene [1913] and

2 Biological Background

Figure 2.6: Three-dimensional reconstructions of the anal somite of a zebrafish embryo in different stages. From [Raamsdonk et al., 1974a].

Shann [1914] (Fig. 2.7(c), (d)). The 3D myotome shape can be described by a cone in the dorsoventral center of the fish, with the apex of the cone directed anteriorly. Then two additional, posteriorly oriented cones are placed dorsally and ventrally to that first cone (Fig. 2.6(c), 2.8).

There are deviations from this general description which make the shape even more complex. Some teleosts show double anterior cones in the posterior somites (Fig. 2.7(b)) [Van Leeuwen, 1999]. Harder [1964] describes that there can be even more cones in other species. About five cones are present in sharks, rays and holocephali and six in bony fish.

2.2 Chevron Pattern in Other Species

The characteristic chevron shape of muscle segments cannot only be found in fish but also in other species. In this section we want to give some examples of such species, making no claim to be complete.

2.2.1 Pikaia

The oldest fossil showing V-shaped chevron currently known is *Pikaia* from lower Cambrian Burgess shales (Fig. 2.9) [Bone and Moore, 2008]. So evolution had at least 500 million years to act on the optimization of body plans involving chevron

2.2 Chevron Pattern in Other Species

(a) Freshly hatched salmon larva. Modified from [Wikipedia, 2009b].

(b) Double anterior cone [Van Leeuwen, 1999].

(c) Longitudinal section through king salmon. From Videler [1993] who modified it from Greene and Greene [1913].

(d) Transverse section. [Shann, 1914]

Figure 2.7: Salmon. (a) W-shape of a somite marked with a black line. (b) Double anterior cone is present in posterior myotomes of some teleost. Figure shows a computational reconstruction. (c) Longitudinal section shows W-shaped somites. (d) Transverse section in the dorsal-left part of a salmon (position indicated by black line in panel (c)). Salmon shows double cone in the posterior somites.

2 Biological Background

Figure 2.8: Myotome of adult cod and mackerel also shows W-shaped chevrons. From [Videler, 1993]

Figure 2.9: Pikaia. From Shu et al. [1996]

patterns.

2.2.2 Ancestral Species

The V-shaped chevron pattern can also be observed in amphioxus (Fig. 2.10), also called lancelet [Bone and Moore, 2008; Somorjai et al., 2008]. Amphioxus is an invertebrate chordate and currently classified as the most ancestral one [Delsuc et al., 2006]. The earliest detailed description of the amphioxus myomeres were done by Nursall [1956]. He also described the myomere shape of lampreys as W-shaped.

Figure 2.10: Amphioxus. One V-shaped chevron marked with blue line. From [Wikipedia, 2009a]

Figure 2.11: A stage 20 *Xenopus* embryo shows V-shaped chevrons in larval stage. From Gray et al. [2009].

2.2.3 Frog

In the tadpole stage the frog is in a wholly aquatic environment and hence experienced the same evolutionary pressure as fish did. It is hence plausible that they share common features in their body plans and indeed the frog *Xenopus* also shows V-shaped chevrons during its embryonic development (Fig. 2.11) [personal communication with David Kimelman].

2.2.4 Mammals

Vertebrates such as mouse, chick and human also form somites and consequently dermatome, myotome and sclerotome. But no chevron shapes can be found, neither in adults nor in their embryonic development. Probably this correlates with the fact that in mouse and chick the major part of the somite becomes sclerotome as opposed to zebrafish where the major part becomes myotome [van Eeden et al., 1996].

2 *Biological Background*

3 State of the Art

In the previous chapter, the biological observations of fish myotome development into its complex shape were presented. Now two questions arise:

First, one might ask why the myotomes are shaped that way. The answer to this question can be found if we keep in mind the main function of the myotomes: They generate the forces needed for swimming. Doing so efficiently provides an evolutionary advantage. Albeit an amount of literature on this topic, there is no complete answer yet. We give a short overview on this in section 3.1.

Second, besides knowing what the function of the chevron pattern is and how it is fulfilled, we have to ask how this structure develops and how the developmental processes constrain its functionality. The ontogenetic development of the myotomes was presented in chapter 2 but we still do not know which processes drive this development. There is far less literature about this aspect and we review it in section 3.2.

3.1 Functional Role of the Chevron Pattern

The main function of the myotomes, driving the locomotion, has been under evolutionary pressure for at least 500 million years [Bone and Moore, 2008]. In consequence the structure has been optimized for the functional demands [Videler, 1993]. Attempts towards understanding if and how the myotomes are functionally optimized tried to explain the complex chevron shape of the myotomes and the muscle fiber orientation within the chevron-shaped myotomes [Hoar et al., 1969].

In particular, muscle fiber orientation in zebrafish and other teleost has been explained by the demand of uniform muscle fiber strain [Alexander, 1969; [van Leeuwen et al., 2008](#)]. Furthermore volume exclusion and the fact that muscle fibers thicken when they contract constrain the fiber orientation [Videler, 1993].

3 *State of the Art*

The attempts to explain myotome shape have not been as successful, yet. The need for oblique myotomes was first noted by Chevrel [1913]. Nursall [1956] proposed that the myosepts that confine the myotomes work as tendons. Van der Stelt [1968] worked out a model that can explain chevron angles for V-shaped myotomes, but fails to explain the need of the complex W-shape in adult fish. The tendon function was disputed by Willemse [1966]. In his view the complex chevron shape brings the advantage of a simplified innervation pattern. More recently Van Leeuwen [1999] argued that, given the muscle fiber orientation in the myotome, the myotomes take on a mechanically stable shape. Still, he fails to explain how muscle fiber orientation and myotome shape interact.

Another idea is put forward by Quentin Bone [Hoar et al., 1969; Bone and Moore, 2008]: There is more myotome ventrally than dorsally. This is due to the viscera which lies ventrally to the notochord and presumably always did in the evolutionary history of the chordate body plan. To avoid bending the dorsoventral axis, he argued, the myotomes are chevron shaped with the apex at the height of the notochord¹.

3.2 Processes that Influence Chevron Formation

Here we want to give an overview of known processes that influence the chevron pattern development and of hypotheses for processes that drive chevron pattern formation.

3.2.1 Movement of the whole Animal

In the 1970s the question for the processes that drive chevron formation was directly addressed by the Dutch group of Raamsdonk et al. [1974a,b, 1977, 1979]. They hypothesized a function of the myotome, namely the movement of the fish, drives chevron formation. Inhibiting the motion of young fish in several experiments, they observed an aberrant development of the chevron pattern. While inhibiting motion, a slight straightening of the chevron was observed. The fish recovered the normal pattern when the fish could move again (Fig. 3.1).

¹Unfortunately he did not prove his idea in his publications. Having mechanical stability in mind, the way it is achieved in corrugated fiberboard, the chevron should be rotated by 90° along the anteroposterior axis, to achieve this function. Attempts to contact Quentin Bone remained unanswered, yet.

3.2 Processes that Influence Chevron Formation

Figure 3.1: Development of somite bending angle (as shown in the upper left of the figure). 180° would mean straight, angle decreases the more the somite bends. Dashed line shows development of untreated embryo. Solid line shows development of embryos that were immobilized by enclosing them in agar. Arrows denote start and end of agar treatment. From [Raamsdonk et al., 1979]

Raamsdonk et al. observed a rather late period in the V-shape formation. We want to denote that the change in angle they observed ($\Delta\beta \approx 20^\circ$, Fig. 3.1) is small compared to the rapid change in angle when the somite starts to bend ($\Delta\beta \approx 80^\circ$, see chapter 4, Data Analysis, Fig. 4.3). Furthermore, opposing to this hypothesis, homozygous *nic^{b107}* zebrafish mutants, which are not able to move, show normal formation of the V-shape pattern [Schröter et al., 2008].

Given this arguments we reject the hypothesis that movements of the whole animal drive chevron pattern formation in fish.

3.2.2 Relative Tissue Displacement

Another hypothesis was formulated by J. Scott Turner. He argues that the myosepts which confine the myotomes are attached to the notochord: The notochord, a rod shaped structure along the anteroposterior axis, extends during development. “The myotome folds into a chevron because it is anchored...[Turner, 2007]” in the notochord.

Interestingly this hypothesis would predict chevrons in the opposite direction with the apex of the chevron in posterior direction. The displacement of the notochord relative to the myotomes can be seen in the supplementary movies from Schröter

Figure 3.2: Zebrafish mutants failing to form the chevron. (a) U-shaped somites in you-mutant. Compare to V-shaped somites of wildtype larva (Fig. 2.1(c)). (b) Near straight somites in ntl mutant.

et al. [2008].

3.2.3 Muscle Cell Differentiation

There exist several zebrafish mutants showing defects in somitogenesis or myogenesis. Here we are interested in mutants which do form somites, but fail to form a proper chevron pattern. A group of mutants, the you-type mutants, were named so, because they form U-shaped somites instead of V-shaped ones (Fig. 3.2(a)). In another mutant, no tail (ntl), the somites stay nearly straight (Fig. 3.2(b)) [van Eeden et al., 1996].

All these mutants do have various defects in muscle development. They have in common to show a deficiency in forming muscle pioneers [van Eeden et al., 1996; Te Kronnie, 2000]. From this evidence we hypothesize defects in muscle cell differentiation during myogenesis, especially in the proper formation of muscle pioneers, lead to failure in chevron pattern formation.

4 Data Analysis

4.1 Method of Measurement

We obtained our data from lightfield microscopy image stacks provided by Christian Schröter [Schröter et al., 2008]. One example picture is shown in Fig. 4.1. The image stacks show the development of embryos from before the 1-somite stage until about the 30 somite stage. The embryos are visible in side view. We measured the angle β as shown in Fig. 4.2(a) for subsequent time points with a software called ImageJ.

The contrast of the segment borders in the light field microscopy images is not very high so there was some uncertainty in the measurement. We therefore measured the minimal and maximal angle consistent with the image as shown by the blue lines in Fig. 4.2(a).

The result of such a measurement for somite 10 is shown in Fig. 4.3. The red solid line in Fig. 4.3 shows an angle $\beta_{measured}$ measured between visually interpolated lines of high segment border contrast and the dashed lines show a $\pm 20^\circ$ error range. This error range approximately corresponds to the error range defined by measured β_{min} and β_{max} as it typically also does for other somites. As measurement of the angles by

Figure 4.1: Lateral view of a 27-somites stage zebrafish embryo. From Schröter et al. [2008]

4 Data Analysis

Figure 4.2: Measurement method. We measured angle β in light field time-lapse movies of dechorionated zebrafish embryos using ImageJ. We calculated $\alpha = 90^\circ - \frac{\beta}{2}$. The movies were provided by Christian Schröter [Schröter et al., 2008].

hand was time consuming, we did not repeat the measurement of β_{min} and β_{max} for other somites but only $\beta_{measured}$, keeping in mind that the error of our measurement is $\pm 20^\circ$.

We measured the angle of each segment border from the timepoint of its appearance. The first eight segments became invisible during observation period. This was not because the segment borders actually vanished but because as the fish gets thicker during development the contrast gets lower. For somites where this happened we assumed that they keep the last measured angle. We could observe segments 9 to 32 from their appearance until the end of the observation time (16 hours). Unfortunately observation time ended before the last few segments could fully form their chevron shape.

Measurements were done for several embryos. Here we only present the data for one typical zebrafish embryo. We also measured and here present data for a *Xenopus* embryo from Gray et al. [2009] (Fig. 2.11). However, only the fully developed chevron and not the time course is available from Gray et al. [2009].

For comparison with our model it will be useful to calculate

$$\alpha = 90 - \frac{\beta}{2}. \quad (4.1.1)$$

The simple geometrical between both angles is shown in Fig. 4.2(b).

Figure 4.3: Measurement of angle β over time for somite 10. $\beta_{measured}$ was measured between visually interpolated lines of high segment border contrast and the dotted lines show a $\pm 20^\circ$ error range of this measurement. β_{min} and β_{max} are the minimal and maximal angle consistent with the image.

4.2 Results

Fig. A.1 (p. 48) shows the complete measured data for one embryo.

Segment borders 1 and 2 remain rather straight (Fig 4.4) and are lost quiet early due to contrast problems. Prominent is that they stay straight when other segment borders already start bending (Fig. 4.4 and A.1). Segment borders 3 and 4 start bending about 30 min after their appearance. Segment border 4 bends more the 3, except for the last data point, which might be erroneous due to low contrast.

Segment borders 4 to 10 bend simultaneously. From them number 7 to 10 clearly reach a plateau at about $\alpha = 40^\circ$ where they do not bend any further (Fig. 4.5).

Later forming borders start bending directly after their formation and therefore bend one after another. They also reach a bending plateau of about $\alpha = 40^\circ$. (Fig. 4.6).

All these results are superimposed in Fig. 4.7 where the data of individual borders i was shifted in time by the time point that border i was originally formed. Then all segment borders start there development at 0 min. Again we observe that the

4 Data Analysis

Figure 4.4: Development of angle α_i for segments 1 to 4.

Figure 4.5: Development of angle α_i for segments 4 to 10. These show sequential formation ($150\text{min} < t < 300\text{min}$) and simultaneous bending of the segment border.

Figure 4.6: Development of angle α_i for segments 19 to 24. These later forming segment borders start bending immediately after their formation. Therefore they bend one after another.

first two segments remain rather straight, the following somites increase their angle. From about somite 10 on all reach an angle of about asymptotic 40° . We can clearly distinguish the datapoints for somites 1 to 7 from the other. The reason is the anterior somites form sequentially but fold simultaneously and hence after shifting the data they are not aligned anymore. Opposed to this the more posterior somites all begin bending directly after segment border formation and do this in a very similar way as superposition of the data reveals.

Additionally, we compare our asymptotic α_i to snapshots in the literature. In Fig 4.8 we present data observed for a *Xenopus* embryo shown in Fig. 2.11. In contrast to zebrafish the monotonic increase in bending here goes from segment 1 to 15 and no clear plateau is reached.

In a 27-somite-stage embryo (Fig. 4.1) nearly all segments are formed. In correspondence to Raamsdonk et al. 1974a and [Kimmel et al. 1995](#) we see that the first two segments remain rather straight (Fig. 4.8). We additionally see a monotonic increase in bending for the first 7 segments which has not been reported elsewhere yet. Segments 8 to 23 form a plateau in bending angle at about 40° .

4 Data Analysis

Figure 4.7: Development of angle α_i for all segments. Data was shifted in time so that all segments formed at their individual $t_i = 0$ min. We clearly can distinguish segments 1 to 7 (delayed bending) from the other (fast and stereotypical bending).

Figure 4.8: Interspecies comparison of asymptotic chevron angles α_i . Red: Zebrafish. Segment border angle over segment number at time 800 min (27-somite stage, as seen in Fig. 4.1). Angles from segment 1-7 could not be measured at this time point and are taken from older time points. We explain the decrease in α for segments 24 to 27 by the fact that they are freshly formed and are just starting to bend. We expect them to also reach the plateau but our data unfortunately ended before this time. Green: Xenopus. Segment border angle over segment number for a stage 29/30 embryo from Gray et al. [2009].

5 Model Derivation

We first describe novel hypotheses for the chevron formation mechanism and evaluate them qualitatively. In section 5.2 we formulate a mathematical model of the interactions between developing muscle fibers and somite boundaries.

5.1 Own Hypotheses

5.1.1 Templating

Possibly the head develops such that it does not have a flat posterior boundary but a chevron shaped one. Now this pattern could be passed to the next somite boundary. Maybe muscle cells just grow to a predefined size, so that when the next boundary connects to the muscle cells this boundary would form a chevron too. The segment posterior to the other segment would mould into the chevron and form a chevron too. Eventually this pattern would be passed to the tail. We call this “templating” [personell communication with Andrew C. Oates].

In contrast to that stand the results of [Riedel-Kruse et al., 2007](#). They switched correct segmentation off and on via DAPT treatment (Fig. 5.1). Although segments 7 to 17 don't form correctly and thereby cannot pass on the pattern, the more posterior segments are shaped normally again.

Furthermore our data analysis showed that the first segments show a gradual increase in chevron angle (Fig 4.8). This cannot be explained simply by templating.

But nevertheless, as the posterior boundary of a segment is the anterior boundary condition for the next segment (the fish tissue is connected!), some information about the shape is passed on from anterior to posterior chevrons.

Figure 5.1: Correct segmentation switched off (somite 8) and on (somite 20) in wild-type zebrafish. From [Riedel-Kruse et al., 2007].

Figure 5.2: Zebrafish. Sketch of heterogeneous force field (arrows indicate forces that may have acted during the shape changes of individual segments). Modified from [Kimmel et al., 1995].

5.1.2 Heterogeneous Force Field

An alternative hypothesis is a heterogeneous force field as function of dorsoventral position that drives the shape change. In zebrafish these forces must act in posterior direction at the dorsal and ventral regions of the somite boundaries. In the center region where the notochord is based they must act in anterior direction (Fig. 5.1.2).

We already excluded relative tissue displacement of the notochord and the somites as a source for these forces as it would act in the opposite direction (see section 3.2.2).

We therefore hypothesize that the differentiating muscle cells could be the source of the heterogeneous force field in the beginning chevron formation. We will illustrate this hypothesis closer in the next chapter.

Figure 5.3: Zebrafish. Somites 15 to 18 at the 18-somite stage. Cells are stained with β -catenin rendering membranes dark. We observed muscle pioneer elongation and chevron formation occur simultaneously. The left boundary (red) already is chevron-shaped. Several elongated muscle pioneers (light blue) attach to it anteriorly. The next boundary is slightly chevron shaped, only one muscle pioneer spans this somite. Other muscle cells (dark blue) start to elongate. Both posterior somites are straight, muscle cells elongate, but none has spanned these somites, yet. Modified from Henry and Amacher [2004].

In chapter 7 we will discuss the occurrence of the additional hinges in later development.

5.1.3 Muscle Pioneer Hypothesis

In section 2.1.4 we stated that muscle pioneer elongation and chevron-pattern formation occur simultaneously (Fig. 5.3). Comparison of findings in muscle cell differentiation and our data analysis strengthens this fact:

The expression of the proteins Eng and MyoD starts simultaneously in the adaxial cells of the first 5-7 somites [Hatta et al., 1991; Weinberg et al., 1996]. This might indicate that cell differentiation, and hence muscle pioneer formation, starts simultaneously in the first few somites. For the more posterior Eng and MyoD are expressed in the somites with a certain time delay after the formation of the respective somite.

5 Model Derivation

Muscle pioneer elongation also starts simultaneously in the first five somites [van Eeden et al., 1996] and then proceeds posteriorly in correspondence to somite formation [Henry and Amacher, 2004]. Our data analysis revealed correlations: Somites 4 to 10 started chevron formation simultaneously and later somites form the chevron sequentially, see Fig. 4.7.

Now, given these correlations, the hypothesis of muscle pioneers driving chevron-pattern formation arises. After spanning the somite medially they might start to contract. Assuming that the anterior border of the first somite is very stiff, the resulting force of this contraction would pull anteriorly on the boundary between first and second somite. The inhomogeneous distribution of the forces on the dorsoventral axis leads to a heterogeneous force field as hypothesized in the previous section, leading to chevron-pattern formation.

To quantify and to understand the effect of several series-connected segments we decided to build up a model that takes up our hypothesis.

5.2 Model Definition

The main elements of our model are n segments. In figure 5.4A three segments are shown. We assume all segments have the same length L . The segment borders are able to fold. We assume the marginal point of the borders to be fixed so the segment length cannot change.

For each segment we need a contracting element which resembles the hypothesized contraction force exerted by the muscle pioneer. Thus we insert a harmonic “contraction-spring” with spring constant K_x^i and extension x_i into each of the n segments as shown in figure 5.4B.

The somite borders in the fish embryo will partly resist against bending and we model this by replacing the border with a second harmonic spring, called “border spring”, in each of the n segments (Fig. 5.4C). These border springs have spring constant K_a^i and extension a_i .

Hence the energy of the system can be written as the sum of the energies of all single harmonic springs in the n segments

$$E_n = \frac{1}{2} \sum_{i=1}^n (K_x^i x_i^2 + K_a^i a_i^2). \quad (5.2.1)$$

Figure 5.4: Model definition. Chain of coupled springs.

a_1 and x_1 have to fulfill the constraint $L = x_1 + a_1$. We set $a_0 \equiv 0$ and are therefore able to write the constraints for all segments as

$$L = x_i + a_i - a_{i-1}, \quad i = 1 \dots n. \quad (5.2.2)$$

We consider the system as damped and therefore aim to find the state of minimal energy. This corresponds to solving the overdamped equation of motion of the system for the systems end state.

By replacing the segment borders with springs, we lost information about the two-dimensional geometry and therefore our model does not say anything directly about the chevron angle. The geometric relation between α_i and the relative border spring extension $\frac{a_i}{L}$ is given by

$$\tan \alpha_i = \frac{2L}{h} \cdot \left(\frac{a_i}{L}\right) = \frac{1}{C} \cdot \left(\frac{a_i}{L}\right), \quad (5.2.3)$$

wherein h is the segment height. The factor $C = \frac{h}{2L}$ is approximately constant throughout all segments, its value is $C \approx 1.3$.

We furthermore note that we could substitute the harmonic potential we intro-

5 *Model Derivation*

duced for the springs by any other potential to examine effects of nonlinear behavior. This possible extension will be discussed in chapter 7.

6 Model Results

6.1 Identical Spring Constants in Each Segment Lead to Exponential Increase in Chevron Angle

6.1.1 Analytical Solution

We want to discuss the simplest case first. Simplest case here means we set identical spring constants for each of the n segments:

$$K_x^i = K_x, \quad K_a^i = K_a, \quad i = 1 \dots n. \quad (6.1.1)$$

Here we will only sketch the calculation. Details can be found in the appendix A.2.1. With (6.1.1) equation (5.2.1) reads:

$$E_n = \frac{1}{2} \sum_{i=1}^n (K_x x_i^2 + K_a a_i^2). \quad (6.1.2)$$

We now introduce the dimensionless variables

$$\tilde{E}_n = \frac{E_n}{K_x L^2}, \quad \tilde{x}_i = \frac{x_i}{L}, \quad \tilde{a}_i = \frac{a_i}{L}, \quad \tilde{K} = \frac{K_a}{K_x}. \quad (6.1.3)$$

Substituting them, equation (6.1.2) reads

$$\tilde{E}_n = \frac{1}{2} \sum_{i=1}^n (\tilde{x}_i^2 + \tilde{K} \tilde{a}_i^2) \quad (6.1.4)$$

and we write the constraints (5.2.2) for the dimensionless variables

$$1 = \tilde{x}_i + \tilde{a}_i - \tilde{a}_{i-1}. \quad (6.1.5)$$

6 Model Results

Substituting the \tilde{x}_i in (6.1.4) with the equations (6.1.5) we get

$$\tilde{E}_n = \frac{1}{2} \sum_{i=1}^n (1 - \tilde{a}_i + \tilde{a}_{i-1})^2 + \tilde{K} \tilde{a}_i^2. \quad (6.1.6)$$

We leave away the tildes for better readability from now on. To get the minimal energy all partial derivatives $\frac{\partial E_n}{\partial a_i}$ must vanish. This leads to a system of n linear equations for the n variables a_i . Solving this system via gaussian elimination leads to the closed form expression for the a_i

$$a_i = \frac{m_{i-1}}{m_n - m_{n-1}}, \quad i = 1 \dots n, \quad (6.1.7)$$

which is expressed with the order 2 linear homogeneous recurrence relation

$$m_{i+1} = \phi m_i - m_{i-1}, \quad m_0 = 1, \quad m_1 = \phi. \quad (6.1.8)$$

This recurrence relation can be solved and leads to

$$a_i = \frac{\lambda_1^i - \lambda_2^i}{C_n}. \quad (6.1.9)$$

C_n , λ_1 and λ_2 are constants just depending on the values of $K = \frac{K_a}{K_x}$ and n :

$$\lambda_{1/2} = \frac{\phi}{2} \pm \sqrt{\frac{\phi^2}{4} - 1} \quad (6.1.10)$$

$$C_n = (\lambda_1^{n+1} - \lambda_1^n) - (\lambda_2^{n+1} - \lambda_2^n) \quad (6.1.11)$$

Where ϕ means

$$\phi = 2 + K \quad (6.1.12)$$

For $K > 0$, a_i will always monotonically increase with a_i with i .

6.1.2 Approximation

To get a better understanding of the solution for the a_i we approximate the result for certain conditions.

6.1 Identical Spring Constants in Each Segment Lead to Exponential Increase in Chevron Angle

Stiff Boundaries

A very stiff boundary means

$$K_a \gg K_x \stackrel{(6.1.3)}{\implies} K \gg 1 \stackrel{(6.1.12)}{\implies} \phi \gg 1. \quad (6.1.13)$$

With that we approximate the square root term in equation (6.1.10):

$$\sqrt{\frac{\phi^2}{4} - 1} \approx \frac{\phi}{2} \quad (6.1.14)$$

and hence

$$\lambda_1 = \phi \quad (6.1.15)$$

$$\lambda_2 = 0. \quad (6.1.16)$$

Now equation (6.1.11) reads

$$C_n = \phi^{n+1} - \phi^n \stackrel{\phi \gg 1}{\approx} \phi^{n+1} \quad (6.1.17)$$

Hence, our solution for a_i is

$$a_i = \frac{\phi^i}{\phi^{n+1}}, \quad (6.1.18)$$

an exponential increase in a_i with respect to i .

Intermediate Boundaries

We note that for $K > 0$ the term under the square root in equation (6.1.10) always is greater than 0, because $\phi = 2 + K$. Consequently

$$\lambda_1 > \lambda_2 \quad (6.1.19)$$

Furthermore from

$$\sqrt{\frac{\phi^2}{4} - 1} < \sqrt{\frac{\phi^2}{4}} = \frac{\phi}{2} \quad (6.1.20)$$

follows that

$$\lambda_2 > 0. \quad (6.1.21)$$

6 Model Results

Figure 6.1: Plots of the relative error $\left(\frac{\lambda_2}{\lambda_1}\right)^i$ over K for $i = 1, 5, 10, 30$ as given by colored lines, see legend. For large i and not too small K the relative error is small.

If we approximate

$$\lambda_1^i - \lambda_2^i \approx \lambda_1^i, \quad (6.1.22)$$

the relative error is

$$\left| \frac{(\lambda_1^i - \lambda_2^i) - \lambda_1^i}{\lambda_1^i} \right| = \left(\frac{\lambda_2}{\lambda_1} \right)^i. \quad (6.1.23)$$

As $\frac{\lambda_2}{\lambda_1} < 1$ the relative error decreases exponentially with i . Hence the approximation is good for large i and not too small K ($i \cdot K \gg 1$, Fig. 6.1). With approximation (6.1.22) we write

$$C_n \approx \lambda_1^{n+1} - \lambda_1^n \quad (6.1.24)$$

and get as our result

$$a_i \approx \frac{\lambda_1^i}{\lambda_1^{n+1} - \lambda_1^n}, \text{ for } i \cdot K \gg 1 \quad (6.1.25)$$

for “intermediate and strong” boundaries. As we saw above this simplifies even more for $K \gg 1$.

6.1.3 Comparing Model Results and Experimental Data

To compare our model results with the experimental data we calculate the α_i from our predicted a_i using equation (5.2.3). For small α_i this equation simplifies to

$$\alpha_i = \frac{a_i}{C}. \quad (6.1.26)$$

Remember $C \approx 1.3$ as stated below equation (5.2.3). Also note that a_i in equation (6.1.26) is the spring extension relative to the segment length as defined in (6.1.3), we just left away the tilde. Our data shows maximum angles of $\alpha_i \approx 45^\circ = \frac{\pi}{4}$. The approximation above will lead to maximum relative errors of

$$\frac{\tan \frac{\pi}{4} - \frac{\pi}{4}}{\tan \frac{\pi}{4}} = 21\%. \quad (6.1.27)$$

As this is in the range of our measurement errors we use the approximation

$$\alpha_i(K) = \frac{a_i}{C} \stackrel{(6.1.9)}{=} \frac{1}{C} \frac{\lambda_1(K)^i - \lambda_2(K)^i}{C_n(K)}, \quad (6.1.28)$$

which depends on the single parameter K , to fit our data. As this function is monotonically nondecreasing we decided to only fit the monotonically nondecreasing regime of our data. For the zebrafish this means we only fit the first 7 somite angles, for the xenopus the first 15 (Fig. 6.2). The results are $K = 0.34$ for zebrafish and $K = 0.12$ for xenopus.

6.2 Special Choices for the Spring Constants lead to Constant or Linearly Increasing Chevron Angle

In the previous section we found that identical spring constants in all segments lead to an exponential increase in angle over segment number (Eq. 6.1.9). We wondered if we are able to find spring constants that lead to linear angle increase or even to constant angles for all segments. Here we only sketch the calculations, detailed calculations are to be found in the appendix (A.2.2). The energy for a system with arbitrary spring constants was given in equation (5.2.1). We substitute the x_i using

6 Model Results

Figure 6.2: Measured data and fitted model prediction. Experimental data is the same as in Fig. 4.8. We fitted function (6.1.28) with Gnuplot, using the nonlinear least-squares Marquardt-Levenberg algorithm. We only fitted the monotonically nondecreasing regime. Hence, for zebrafish (red) we used the first 7, for xenopus (green) we used the first 15 data points for the fit.

equation (5.2.2):

$$E_n = \frac{1}{2} \sum_{i=1}^n (K_x^i (L - a_i + a_{i-1})^2 + K_a^i a_i^2). \quad (6.2.1)$$

We introduce dimensionless variables:

$$\tilde{E}_n = \frac{E_n}{KL^2}, \quad \tilde{x}_i = \frac{x_i}{L}, \quad \tilde{a}_i = \frac{a_i}{L}, \quad \tilde{K}_x^i = \frac{K_x^i}{K}, \quad \tilde{K}_a^i = \frac{K_a^i}{K} \quad (6.2.2)$$

Substituting with the dimensionless variables in equation (6.2.1) we get

$$\tilde{E}_n = \frac{1}{2} \sum_{i=1}^n \tilde{K}_x^i (1 - \tilde{a}_i + \tilde{a}_{i-1})^2 + \tilde{K}_a^i \tilde{a}_i^2. \quad (6.2.3)$$

From now we leave away the tildes. Analogous to (6.1.4) minimizing the energy leads to a system of n linear equations for the n variables a_i . But as this time $2n$ parameters, the n K_x^i and the n K_a^i , are to choose we cannot find a short closed form expression for the a_i , as in the case with identical spring constants in each segment. So instead of solving the general system we will make an ansatz for the a_i and find

6.2 Special Choices for the Spring Constants lead to Constant or Linearly Increasing Chevron Angle

(a) i dependency of contraction spring constants relative to border spring constant.

(b) Border extensions a_i show linear increase with i .

Figure 6.3: Example for i dependency of contraction spring constant that lead to linear increase in a_i . Here we chose constant border springs K_a and $m = \frac{1}{300}$. Then, $\frac{K_x^i}{K_a}$ was calculated using equation (6.2.5).

under which conditions it can be fulfilled.

The ansatz of a linear increase

$$a_i = m \cdot i \quad (6.2.4)$$

yields that the K_x^i and K_a^i have to fulfill the following condition:

$$m = \frac{K_x^2 - K_x^1}{K_x^2 - K_x^1 - K_a^1} = \frac{K_x^3 - K_x^2}{K_x^3 - K_x^2 - 2K_a^2} = \dots \\ \dots = \frac{K_x^{i+1} - K_x^i}{K_x^{i+1} - K_x^i - iK_a^i} = \dots = \frac{K_x^n}{K_x^n + nK_a^n}. \quad (6.2.5)$$

Constant $K_x^i = K_x$ lead to the trivial case

$$m = \frac{K_x - K_x}{K_x - K_x - iK_a^i} = 0. \quad (6.2.6)$$

For $m > 0$, $K_x^{i+1} > K_x^i$ follows from (6.2.5). With constant $K_a^i = K_a$ it is still possible to fulfill (6.2.5) (Fig. 6.3).

The ansatz of constant a_i

$$a_i = a \quad (6.2.7)$$

6 Model Results

Figure 6.4: Example for i dependency of contraction spring constant that lead to constant a_i . Here we chose constant border springs K_a and $a_i = a = 0.1$. Then, $\frac{K_x^i}{K_a}$ was calculated using equation (6.2.8).

leads to the condition

$$a = \frac{K_x^1 - K_x^2}{K_a^1 + K_x^1} = \frac{K_x^2 - K_x^3}{K_a^2} = \dots = \frac{K_x^i - K_x^{i+1}}{K_a^i} = \dots = \frac{K_x^n}{K_a^n}. \quad (6.2.8)$$

which has to be fulfilled by the K_x^i and K_a^i . Again, constant $K_x^i = K_x$ would lead to a trivial case:

$$a = \frac{K_x - K_x}{K_a^i} = 0. \quad (6.2.9)$$

Choosing constant $K_a^i = K_a$, we need linear decreasing K_x^i (with an exception for K_x^1 , Fig. 6.4) to achieve constant a_i for all segments.

6.3 Robustness of Cheron Angle Results against Spring Variability

The segments of the fish are not precisely identical, systematic as well as random differences between the segments do exist, e.g. of segment length and height. However, identical spring constants in all segments were used, for the results from section 6.1. This, of course, is a very high symmetry in the system, which the fish does not exactly fulfill. Possibly, already small random variations from segment to seg-

6.3 Robustness of Cheron Angle Results against Spring Variability

ment could lead to a completely different solution. To test our approximation for consistency, we decided to vary the spring constant $K_{a,x}$ in the following way:

$$K_{a,x}^i = (1 + \Delta_i)K_{a,x} \quad (6.3.1)$$

with Δ_i being normally distributed random variables with mean $\langle \Delta_i \rangle = 0$ and standard deviation σ . For unphysiological instances of $\Delta_i < -1$, and therefore negative $K_{a,x}^i$, we set the corresponding $K_{a,x} = 0$. The minimization of the corresponding energy of the system with randomly varied $K_{a,x}^i$ again leads to a system of n linear equations. But a short closed form expression for this system cannot be given. Hence, we decided to study examples of such systems for certain outcomes of the random variables by numerically solving the corresponding system of linear equations. The implementation was done in Mathematica.

The solution (6.1.9) for the system with identical spring constants only depends on the ratio $\frac{K_a}{K_x}$. We found the same for the system with randomly varied spring constants. We did a closer examination of the cases where we fitted the results to the data ($\{K = 0.34, n = 7\}$, $\{K = 0.12, n = 15\}$). For relative errors smaller than 1% the solution shows the same qualitative behavior as for the deterministic case. The absolute deviations are of the same order for all segments, hence the relative deviations for the first segments are the largest.

We studied the robustness of the results in section 6.2 analogously to the above case and obtained qualitatively identical results as above (see Fig. 6.5 for an example).

6 Model Results

Figure 6.5: Robustness against spring constant variation.

7 Discussion

How functional laws, functional demands and evolutionary pressure influenced the chevron-pattern of the somites in fish has long been discussed [e.g. Greene and Greene, 1913; Nursall, 1956; van Leeuwen et al., 2008] but the influence of developmental mechanisms has been neglected, with few exceptions [Raamsdonk et al., 1974a; Turner, 2007]. We showed that the mechanisms proposed in the literature are insufficient to explain beginning chevron pattern formation. Our data analysis revealed, in good correspondence to experiments on muscle cell differentiation [Hatta et al., 1991; Weinberg et al., 1996], the existence of two groups of somites: The first, comprising the anteriormost few, which undergo chevron formation simultaneously and the second, comprising the posterior somites, which form the chevron sequentially. The insufficiency in current hypotheses led us to formulate the “Muscle Pioneer Hypothesis” which involves that contracting muscle pioneer cells in the medial region of the somites drive the beginning chevron pattern formation. To validate our hypothesis we built up a mathematical model, of the interactions between developing muscle fibers and somite boundaries, the results of which we compared with the experimental data we obtained.

7.1 Comparison of Experimental Data and Model

Results

In section 6.1 we were able to show that our model can explain the increase in chevron angle against somite number observed in the first group if we assume identical spring constants for all segments (Fig. 6.2). The model predicts the forces exerted by the contractions being three times larger than those exerted by the segment borders in zebrafish ($K = \frac{K_a}{K_x} = 0.34 \approx \frac{1}{3}$). Interspecies comparison showed the bending increase in xenopus to be less steep (Fig. 6.2). Hence one might think that the contraction

7 Discussion

forces are smaller with respect to the stiffness of the segment borders. However, our model counterintuitively predicts the opposite: $\frac{K_a}{K_x} = 0.12 \approx \frac{1}{10}$. The forces exerted by the contractions are ten times larger than those exerted by the segment borders in xenopus.

To explain the constant angle for the posterior somites with our model we have to finetune our parameters K_x^i and K_a^i so that they fulfill equation (6.2.8). For constant $K_a^i = K_a$ this would mean linearly decreasing K_x^i (Fig. 6.4). However, there is no biological evidence for decreasing muscle fiber strength throughout the fish nor is it clear how the fish should manage to finetune the spring constants.

Here the limitations of our model are clearly visible: We tried to explain a tissue that we expect to have nonlinear elastic properties and even to be inelastic with a model that assumes ideal linear elastic properties.

7.2 Proposed Experiments for Verification

Clearly, a next step to validate our hypothesis is to design experiments.

Our data analysis was subject to two problems: First, the measurement error for β of $\pm 20^\circ$ is large. Second, we lost somite borders due to contrast problems. In zebrafish it is possible to stain the boundary to get a high contrast [personell communication with Andy Oates]. Unfortunately the fish have to be killed and fixed, therewith the chevron angle could change. By comparing our data with that of fixed, stained boundary embryos this could be excluded. Then data with less error and over the whole development period can be obtained.

In another experiment temporal correlation of muscle pioneer elongation (e.g. relative elongation of the longest cell with respect to the somite length) and chevron angle development could be measured. This should be possible with Laser Scanning Microscopy and the right staining.

If this experiment succeeds in showing temporal correlation, in another step, muscle pioneers could be disrupted via laser ablation, without harming the surrounding tissues [personell communication with Carl-Philipp Heisenberg]. Our hypothesis would predict that this treatment interferes with chevron pattern formation.

7.3 Open Questions and Alternative Modeling Approaches

7.3.1 Nonlinear Energy Potential

In section 5.2 we stated the possibility to substitute the harmonic springs we use in our model with nonlinear ones. By doing so, we would hope that our model then accounts for aspects that are not covered yet, e.g. that it shows angle increase for anterior and saturation for posterior somites. For instance, preliminary results indicate that introducing a rest length L_0 for the contraction springs and assuming a Hill function like potential for the border springs

$$E_n = \frac{1}{2} \sum_{i=1}^n \left(K_x^i (x_i - L_0)^2 + K_a^i a_i^2 \frac{a_h^2}{a_i^2 + a_h^2} \right) \quad (7.3.1)$$

lead to linear increase in a_i . The advantage of this model over the achievement of linear increase with the model in section 6.2 is that we do not need to tune our parameters K_x^i and K_a^i . Instead we can use identical parameters, K_x , K_a , for all segments.

The goal of finding and interpreting a nonlinear potential that accounts for angle increase for anterior and saturation for posterior somites could not be achieved in this thesis. But the possibility of an extension of our model in this direction is clear and could be done in further work on this topic.

7.3.2 Chevron Instabilities

There exist systems showing chevron pattern formation that, at first glance, seem to be unrelated to fish. We wondered if, beyond the observation of chevron, a functional correlation could underly them.

Chevron Instability in Extended Dissipative Systems

Extended dissipative systems can show formation of patterns when they are driven away from equilibrium [[Bowman and Newell, 1998](#)]. Among stripes, spirals, target and hexagonal patterns also chevron patterns (also denoted zigzag pattern) emerge. In nematic liquid crystals, which are an example for such a system, the chevron

Figure 7.1: Sketch of layered material. Black marks the hard phase, in between is a soft, rubbery phase. (a) Globally aligned layered material, e.g. SIS, is stretched. (b) Above a critical strain buckling of the layers occurs and they form a chevron pattern [Read et al., 1999].

pattern can emerge out of the homogeneous state, showing typical chevron angles and typical layer spacing [Rossberg and Kramer, 1998; Komineas et al., 2003].

The mathematical tool of choice to describe the emergence of such patterns are amplitude equations. The appropriate amplitude equation that allows chevron solutions in homogeneous systems is the Newell-Whitehead-Segal equation [Bowman and Newell, 1998].

However, the muscle differentiation process is inherently heterogeneous. Muscle pioneers may already pull on segment borders while other muscle cells still need to connect to the borders. Therefore, the amplitude equation formalism would have to be significantly extended.

Chevron Instability in Layered Systems

Under mechanical stress chevron patterns can emerge in layered systems with layers straight and parallel in the initial state. Layered systems that show chevron structures under stress are for example polymers [Read et al., 1999], smectic liquid crystals, geological structures and magnetic films [Singer, 1993].

Models for the chevron instability in layered materials already exist [e.g. Read et al., 1999]. Their model describes a two dimensional copolymer, consisting of layers of a thin hard, glassy phase and a soft, rubbery phase. For such materials, e.g. styrene-isoprene-styrene (SIS), a buckling instability is observed when they are exposed to dilative strain perpendicular to the layers (Fig. 7.1).

To analytically describe the onset of buckling Read et al. use a mean local energy

7.3 Open Questions and Alternative Modeling Approaches

Figure 7.2: Finite element simulation of single layer with periodic boundary conditions. From (a) to (d) homogeneous vertical pulling forces increase. A transition from straight and parallel boundaries via sinusoidal buckling towards a chevron morphology is observed. [Read et al., 1999]

which shows an instability against buckling above a critical strain threshold. This initial buckling is sinusoidal and has a certain wavevector k . Furthermore they perform numerical simulations using finite element methods to investigate behavior after initial buckling. Thereby they find that after initial sinusoidal buckling a transition to a chevron morphology occurs (Fig. 7.2).

We imagine that a similar model could be used for fish if a homogeneous force field would be available. We regard the somite boundaries as the hard phase and the muscle tissue in between as the soft phase. The dynamics of somite boundary shapes then could be explained by a raising homogeneous force field either dilating the somites anteroposteriorly or compressing them in the dorsoventral direction. Potentially different fish species with different dorsoventral sizes may accommodate different numbers of buckling wavelengths thereby showing different numbers of hinges (Fig. 7.3). In the simulation of perfectly aligned layers, amplitudes of the wave are constant whereas salmon shows varying amplitudes (Fig. 2.1(a) and 2.7). This is not surprising as fish do not represent perfect material but show many complex structures.

It is still unclear which mechanism could be responsible for the required stress field. The mechanism could somehow be related to the convergent extension of the fish and the corresponding cell transports. However it is possible that no actual stress field

Figure 7.3: Buckling of finite element multilayer under dilative strain perpendicular to the layers. Here the left (A=anterior) and right (P=posterior) boundaries are constrained to be flat. Potentially different fish species overspan different regions. Solid lines show dorsal and ventral borders of fish, dashed line is dorsoventral symmetry axis.

is applied but rather the muscle fibers connect the somite boundaries. These could then start to act similar to the stretched molecules in the soft phase. One interesting idea is that actively contracting muscles provide forces equivalent to the stretched molecules of the soft phase.

8 Conclusion

In this thesis we reviewed the literature about the function and the mechanisms underlying the emergence of the chevron shape in the myotome of fish. We found there is a lack in knowledge about the latter. Therefore it remains unclear, how developmental mechanisms constrain myotome patterns and in how far functional demands of efficient swimming can be fulfilled.

With the “Muscle Pioneer Hypothesis” we postulated a novel mechanism to explain the chevron pattern development in fish. We supported our hypothesis by formulating it in terms of a mathematical model. With our model we were able to explain the increase in chevron angle throughout the anterior somites in the beginning chevron development. The increasing chevron angles for the anterior somites clearly are a constraint for the shaping of the body segments. When development is neglected, one might think of functional demands fulfilled by the increasing chevron angles, but this is irrelevant, because the fish’s chevron building mechanism can only build chevrons with increasing angle.

An explanation for the saturation in chevron angle in the posterior somites was not achieved, but we outlined how our model could be extended to account for this. We proposed experiments that can validate or falsify our hypothesis. The emergence of the W-shape in later fish development could not be explained in this thesis. However, we compared the emergence of chevron patterns in other systems with the emergence of the chevron pattern in fish and propose that extension of the ideas from other systems towards the fish might be possible.

8 *Conclusion*

A Appendix

A.1 Experimental Data

Figure A.1: Development of segment border angle α_i over time for somites 1 to 32. The data points were approximated with 32 fitted Bezier curves. Raw data can be supplied by the author on demand.

A.2 Explicit Calculations

A.2.1 Minimal Energy Configuration for the Chain of Coupled Springs with Identical Spring Constants

We will minimize the energy function to find the equilibrium state.

The total energy E_n of a chain with n segments is the sum over the energy of each single spring:

$$E_n = \frac{1}{2} \sum_{i=1}^n (K_x x_i^2 + K_a a_i^2) \quad (\text{A.2.1})$$

copied this into model definition: a_i and x_i have to fullfill the constraint $L = x_i + a_i$. We set $a_0 \equiv 0$ and are therefore able to write the constraints for all segments as

$$L = x_i + a_i - a_{i-1}, \quad i = 1 \dots n. \quad (\text{A.2.2})$$

We now introduce the dimensionless variables

$$\tilde{E}_n = \frac{E_n}{K_x L^2}, \quad \tilde{x}_i = \frac{x_i}{L}, \quad \tilde{a}_i = \frac{a_i}{L}, \quad \tilde{K} = \frac{K_a}{K_x}. \quad (\text{A.2.3})$$

Using equations (5.2.1) and (5.2.2) we get

$$\tilde{E}_n = \frac{1}{2} \sum_{i=1}^n (\tilde{x}_i^2 + \tilde{K} \tilde{a}_i^2) \quad (\text{A.2.4})$$

for our dimensionless energy \tilde{E}_n and we can write the constraints for our dimensionless variables as

$$1 = \tilde{x}_i + \tilde{a}_i - \tilde{a}_{i-1}. \quad (\text{A.2.5})$$

Substituting the \tilde{x}_i in (6.1.4) with the equations (6.1.5) we get

$$\tilde{E}_n = \frac{1}{2} \sum_{i=1}^n (1 - \tilde{a}_i + \tilde{a}_{i-1})^2 + \tilde{K} \tilde{a}_i^2. \quad (\text{A.2.6})$$

We will leave away the tildes for better readability from now on. A necessary condition for E_n to be minimal is the disappearance of all partial derivatives of E_n with

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respect to all a_j . We therefore calculate

$$0 \stackrel{!}{=} \frac{\partial E_n}{\partial a_j} = -a_{j-1} + (2 + K)a_j - a_n \delta_{nj} - a_{j+1} - \delta_{nj}, \quad j = 1 \dots n, \quad (\text{A.2.7})$$

where we set $a_0 \equiv 0$. This is a system of linear equations which we can write as a matrix equation:

$$\begin{pmatrix} 2+K & -1 & 0 & \cdots & \cdots & 0 \\ -1 & 2+K & -1 & 0 & \cdots & \vdots \\ 0 & \ddots & \ddots & \ddots & & \vdots \\ \vdots & & \ddots & \ddots & \ddots & 0 \\ \vdots & \cdots & 0 & -1 & 2+K & -1 \\ 0 & \cdots & \cdots & 0 & -1 & 1+K \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} a_1 \\ a_2 \\ \vdots \\ \vdots \\ a_{n-1} \\ a_n \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ \vdots \\ \vdots \\ 0 \\ 1 \end{pmatrix} \quad (\text{A.2.8})$$

With $\phi = 2 + K$ we can write the augmented matrix of the system as

$$\left[\begin{array}{cccccc|c} \phi & -1 & 0 & \cdots & \cdots & 0 & 0 \\ -1 & \phi & -1 & & & \vdots & 0 \\ 0 & \ddots & \ddots & \ddots & & \vdots & \vdots \\ \vdots & & \ddots & \ddots & \ddots & 0 & \vdots \\ \vdots & & & -1 & \phi & -1 & 0 \\ 0 & \cdots & \cdots & 0 & -1 & \phi - 1 & 1 \end{array} \right]. \quad (\text{A.2.9})$$

We solve the system via gaussian elimination. Eliminating the lower secondary diagonal is our first goal. Therefore our first step is to add the first row of (A.2.9) to ϕ times the second row, which gives us

$$\left[\begin{array}{cccccc|c} \phi & -1 & 0 & \cdots & \cdots & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \phi^2 - 1 & -\phi & 0 & \cdots & 0 & 0 \\ \vdots & -1 & \phi & -1 & & 0 & 0 \\ & & \ddots & \ddots & \ddots & \vdots & \vdots \end{array} \right]. \quad (\text{A.2.10})$$

A.2 Explicit Calculations

We go on further, adding the second row to $(\phi^2 - 1)$ times the third row:

$$\left[\begin{array}{cccc|c} \phi & -1 & 0 & \cdots & 0 \\ 0 & \phi^2 - 1 & -\phi & 0 & \cdots & 0 \\ \vdots & 0 & \phi^3 - 2\phi & -(\phi^2 - 1) & & 0 \\ & & \ddots & \ddots & \ddots & \vdots \end{array} \right]. \quad (\text{A.2.11})$$

Doing so until we reach the $(n - 1)^{\text{th}}$ row we get a matrix in the form

$$\left[\begin{array}{cccc|c} m_{11} & m_{12} & 0 & \cdots & 0 \\ 0 & m_{22} & m_{23} & 0 & 0 \\ \vdots & \ddots & \ddots & \ddots & \vdots \\ & & 0 & m_{n-1,n-1} & m_{n-1,n} \\ & & & -1 & \phi - 1 & 1 \end{array} \right]. \quad (\text{A.2.12})$$

The matrix entries recursively depend on the previous row in the following way:

$$m_{i,i+1} = -m_{i-1,i-1} \quad (\text{A.2.13})$$

$$m_{i,i} = \phi m_{i-1,i-1} - m_{i-2,i-2}. \quad (\text{A.2.14})$$

We define the sequence m_i by the recurrence relation

$$m_{i+1} = \phi m_i - m_{i-1}, \quad m_0 = 1, m_1 = \phi \quad (\text{A.2.15})$$

and use it to write the matrix (A.2.12) as

$$\left[\begin{array}{cccc|c} m_1 & -m_0 & 0 & \cdots & 0 \\ 0 & m_2 & -m_1 & 0 & 0 \\ \vdots & \ddots & \ddots & \ddots & \vdots \\ & & 0 & m_{n-1} & -m_{n-2} \\ & & & -1 & \phi - 1 & 1 \end{array} \right]. \quad (\text{A.2.16})$$

Adding the $(n-1)$ th row to m_{n-1} times the n th row we eliminated the lower secondary

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diagonal and get

$$\left[\begin{array}{cccc|c} m_1 & -m_0 & 0 & \cdots & 0 \\ 0 & m_2 & -m_1 & 0 & 0 \\ \vdots & \ddots & \ddots & \ddots & \vdots \\ & & 0 & m_{n-1} & -m_{n-2} \\ & & & 0 & m_n - m_{n-1} \end{array} \middle| m_{n-1} \right]. \quad (\text{A.2.17})$$

We are now going to eliminate the upper secondary diagonal. We start by adding m_{n-2} times the n th row to $(m_n - m_{n-1})$ times the $(n - 1)$ th row. Reducing by m_{n-1} we get

$$\left[\begin{array}{cccc|c} m_1 & -m_0 & 0 & \cdots & 0 \\ 0 & m_2 & -m_1 & 0 & 0 \\ \vdots & \ddots & \ddots & \ddots & \vdots \\ & & 0 & m_n - m_{n-1} & 0 \\ & & & 0 & m_n - m_{n-1} \end{array} \middle| m_{n-2} \right]. \quad (\text{A.2.18})$$

Going backwards through the whole matrix again we finally get a diagonal matrix

$$\left[\begin{array}{cccc|c} m_n - m_{n-1} & & & & m_0 \\ & m_n - m_{n-1} & & & m_1 \\ & & \ddots & & \vdots \\ & & & m_n - m_{n-1} & m_{n-2} \\ & & & & m_n - m_{n-1} \end{array} \middle| m_{n-1} \right] \quad (\text{A.2.19})$$

and therefore

$$a_i = \frac{m_{i-1}}{m_n - m_{n-1}}, \quad i = 1 \dots n. \quad (\text{A.2.20})$$

Equation (A.2.15) is an order 2 linear homogeneous recurrence relation. We will solve it to get a closed form expression for m_i and hence for a_i . Thus, instead of equation (A.2.15) we write the matrix equation

$$\begin{pmatrix} m_{i+1} \\ m_i \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} \phi & -1 \\ 1 & 0 \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} m_i \\ m_{i-1} \end{pmatrix}. \quad (\text{A.2.21})$$

We define $M = \begin{pmatrix} \phi & -1 \\ 1 & 0 \end{pmatrix}$ and use equation (A.2.21) $i + 1$ times to get

$$\begin{aligned} \begin{pmatrix} m_{i+1} \\ m_i \end{pmatrix} &= M \begin{pmatrix} m_i \\ m_{i-1} \end{pmatrix} = M^2 \begin{pmatrix} m_{i-1} \\ m_{i-2} \end{pmatrix} = \\ &\dots = M^{i-1} \begin{pmatrix} m_1 \\ m_0 \end{pmatrix} = M^{i-1} \begin{pmatrix} \phi \\ 1 \end{pmatrix}. \end{aligned} \quad (\text{A.2.22})$$

The eigenvalues and eigenvectors of M are

$$\lambda_{1/2} = \frac{\phi}{2} \pm \sqrt{\frac{\phi^2}{4} - 1} \quad (\text{A.2.23})$$

$$\underline{e}_{1/2} = \begin{pmatrix} \lambda_{1/2} \\ 1 \end{pmatrix}. \quad (\text{A.2.24})$$

$\begin{pmatrix} \phi \\ 1 \end{pmatrix}$ can be represented by a combination of the eigenvectors of M :

$$\begin{pmatrix} \phi \\ 1 \end{pmatrix} = c_1 \underline{e}_1 + c_2 \underline{e}_2, \quad (\text{A.2.25})$$

$$c_1 = \frac{\lambda_1}{\sqrt{\phi^2 - 4}} \quad (\text{A.2.26})$$

$$c_2 = \frac{-\lambda_2}{\sqrt{\phi^2 - 4}}. \quad (\text{A.2.27})$$

We use (A.2.25) in (A.2.22) and get

$$\begin{pmatrix} m_{i+1} \\ m_i \end{pmatrix} = M^{i-1} (c_1 \underline{e}_1 + c_2 \underline{e}_2) = c_1 \lambda_1^{i-1} \begin{pmatrix} \lambda_1 \\ 1 \end{pmatrix} + c_2 \lambda_2^{i-1} \begin{pmatrix} \lambda_2 \\ 1 \end{pmatrix}. \quad (\text{A.2.28})$$

The equation for the second component of this is the closed form expression for m_i :

$$m_i = \frac{\lambda_1^{i+1} - \lambda_2^{i+1}}{\sqrt{\phi^2 - 4}} \quad (\text{A.2.29})$$

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With

$$\frac{1}{C_n} = \sqrt{\phi^2 - 4} (m_n - m_{n-1}) = (\lambda_1^{n+1} - \lambda_1^n) - (\lambda_2^{n+1} - \lambda_2^n), \quad (\text{A.2.30})$$

which is a constant for a chain with n segments, the closed form expression for a_i is

$$a_i = \frac{\lambda_1^i - \lambda_2^i}{C_n}. \quad (\text{A.2.31})$$

A.2.2 Calculating Spring Constants that Lead to Constant or Linearly Increasing Chevron Angle

We start minimizing the dimensionless energy (6.2.3)

$$E_n = \frac{1}{2} \sum_{i=1}^n K_x^i (1 - a_i + a_{i-1})^2 + K_a^i a_i^2. \quad (\text{A.2.32})$$

For the minimum all partial derivatives $\frac{\partial E_n}{\partial a_i}$ must vanish. Analogous to the case with identical spring constants this leads to a system of n linear equations for the n variables a_i . The augmented matrix for arbitrary spring constants reads

$$\left[\begin{array}{cccccc|c} -(K_a^1 + K_x^1 + K_x^2) & K_x^2 & 0 & \cdots & \cdots & 0 & K_x^2 - K_x^1 \\ K_x^2 & -(K_a^2 + K_x^2 + K_x^3) & K_x^3 & & & \vdots & K_x^3 - K_x^2 \\ 0 & \ddots & \ddots & \ddots & & \vdots & \vdots \\ \vdots & & \ddots & \ddots & \ddots & 0 & \vdots \\ \vdots & & & 0 & K_x^n & -(K_a^n + K_x^n) & -K_x^n \end{array} \right]. \quad (\text{A.2.33})$$

Linearly Increasing Chevron Angle

We substitute

$$a_i = m \cdot i \quad (\text{A.2.34})$$

in the system (A.2.33). Hence, the first row reads

$$-(K_a^1 + K_x^1 + K_x^2) \cdot m + K_x^2 \cdot 2m = K_x^2 - K_x^1. \quad (\text{A.2.35})$$

$$\implies m = \frac{K_x^2 - K_x^1}{K_x^2 - K_a^1 - K_x^1} \quad (\text{A.2.36})$$

We do this for every row. The i th row leads to

$$m = \frac{K_x^{i+1} - K_x^i}{K_x^{i+1} - K_x^i - iK_a^i} \quad (\text{A.2.37})$$

except for the n th row which leads to

$$m = \frac{K_x^n}{K_x^n + nK_a^n} \quad (\text{A.2.38})$$

Equations (A.2.37) and (A.2.38) together give equation (6.2.5).

Constant Chevron Angle

This time we substitute

$$a_i = a \quad (\text{A.2.39})$$

in the system (A.2.33). Analogous to the above case we now write down the explicit equation for every row. This finally leads to equation (6.2.8).

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Acknowledgements

I thank Prof. Roland Ketzmerick, Prof. Andreas Deutsch and Dr. Lutz Brusch for making this thesis possible. I thank the whole IMC group for discussions and the friendly atmosphere. I thank Andrew C. Oates and Christian Schröter for giving me the movies and for discussion. I thank Sabine, Paulina, my parents and my friends for making me happy.

Erklärung

Hiermit versichere ich, dass ich die vorliegende Arbeit ohne unzulässige Hilfe Dritter und ohne Benutzung anderer als der angegebenen Hilfsmittel angefertigt habe. Die aus fremden Quellen direkt oder indirekt übernommenen Gedanken sind als solche kenntlich gemacht. Die Arbeit wurde bisher weder im Inland noch im Ausland in gleicher oder ähnlicher Form einer anderen Prüfungsbehörde vorgelegt.

Fabian Rost

Dresden, 25.01.2010